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Impact of Rubber Orchards (*Hevea Brasiliensis* Muell. Arg.) On Termite Communities in West of Côte d'Ivoire

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Abstract

Perennial crops influence ecosystems and insect dynamics. The study was carried out to evaluate the influence of rubber orchards age and forest on termite's diversity and to determine their feeding groups in Tonkpi region of Côte d'Ivoire. Termites were sampled in transects of 100 m long and 10 m wide in 3 classes of rubber orchards (class 1:] 0, 5] years), class 2:] 5, 10] years and class 3:] 10, 15] years) in comparison to forest. Termites harvested at four trophic groups: wood-feeders, grass/litter feeders, fungus-growers and soil-feeders. A total of 09 species of termites belonging to 09 genera and 4 sub-families were collected in all the study plots. The Cubitermitinae and Macrotermitinae families were more diversified with 3 genera of termite. In young rubber orchards (]0, 5] years old) and in rubber orchards of class 3, a total of 5 species of termites were collected. Class 2 recorded the lowest diversity with 4 genera of termites collected. Forest recorded the highest diversity with 7 genera of termites collected. The termite attacks decreases progressively with the age and were between 8 to 82%. The number of termite's mounds increased with the dry vegetables occurred in rubber orchards. We recommended that the combination of other plants to rubber crops for the termite's diversity conservation.

Keywords: Biodiversity, forest, *Hevea brasiliensis*, termites, Côte d'Ivoire

1. INTRODUCTION

Rubber tree (*Hevea brasiliensis* Muell. Arg.) is a perennial tree belonging to the Euphorbiaceae family. The rubber tree is native to Brazil and was exclusively cultivated for the quality of the latex (Keli *et al.*, 1997; Kougbo *et al.*, 2020). Since 2000, rubber plantations were become an important cash crop in Côte d'Ivoire. Rubber orchards production was 94,000 tons of latex and was covering 80,000 hectares (Keli *et al.*, 1997). Rubber orchards influence ecosystems and insect dynamics. They actively participate in the stability of ecosystems by pollinating plants, breaking down dead matter and serving as the basis of the food web. In addition, insects are excellent indicators of biodiversity and are thought to reflect the vegetation in place (Buchori *et al.*, 2018). Indeed, the presence of some insects, in particular termites and hymenoptera, showed that their habitat was sound and allow good conservation of biodiversity (Muvengwi *et al.*, 2017; Diabaté and Tano, 2020). Termites (Isoptera) are invertebrates that play many ecological functions in terrestrial ecosystems, especially in tropical areas (Eggleton, 2000; Sane *et al.*, 2016). During the dry season, termites constitute the most active soil macrofauna (Diop *et al.*, 2013). In search of food, termites attack fresh and dry grasses and they break down them into organic matter (Rosin and Leponce, 2004). So that, termites impacts the quality and the fertility of the soil (Jouquet *et al.*, 2011; Freymann *et al.*, 2008). However, termites infests various parts of rubber trees including roots, stem and branches and cause significant damage to crops in tropical regions (Han and Ndiaye, 1998; Akpessa *et al.*, 2008). Perennial crops such as rubber orchards indirectly through microclimate change (Hunter, 2007) and represent a highest importance to insect biodiversity and to insect abundance (Diniz *et al.*, 2010; Elia *et al.*, 2012; Muvengwi *et al.*, 2017).

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However, its production is threatened by several biotic factors, especially termites. However, few studies have been carried out on the impact of perennial crops on insect biodiversity. The study was carried out in Tonkpi region (Man, Côte d'Ivoire) to evaluate the influence of rubber orchards age and forest on termite's diversity and to determine their feeding groups.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1. Study area

The study was carried out in the region of Tonkpi in the West of Côte d'Ivoire (Figure 1). Tonkpi region is located at 7°24'N and 7°33'W. The study area was influenced by the subequatorial climate. The mean of annual rainfall was 1632 mm and the average annual temperature was 25 °C. The rainy season was seven-months from April to October (Saley, 2003; Brou, 2005; Ahoussi *et al.*, 2018). This region was an agro-ecological area which showed climatic conditions favorable for rubber cultivation. The vegetation was forests marked in places by meadows (Brou, 2005).

Figure 1. Location of data collection sites in west of Côte d'Ivoire (Man)

2.2. Experimental design

The study was conducted from February to April, 2021 to evaluate the influence of rubber orchards age and forest on termite's species and their damages. These insects damages were collected in forest and in rubber orchards (class 1:] 0, 5] years), class 2:] 5, 10] years and class 3:] 10, 15] years) (Table 1). Three plots of 1 ha (10 m x 100 m) per rubber orchards class and in the forest were sampled. Rubber trees were spaced at 7 m x 2.8 m.

The Rubber trees used to the studies were *Hevea brasiliensis* (Mueller Argoviensis Euphorbiaceae) PB 260 clones, belonging to the class of rapid metabolic activity. In addition, forests (25 years old) were used for termites sampling.

2.3. Termite sampling

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Termites were sampled in transects of 100 m long and 10 m wide (Eggleton, 2000) from February, to April 2021. The transects were subdivided into 3 sections. Sampling was carried out between 7:00 to 11:00 from a forest and rubber orchards. In each section, the number of termite mounds and rubber trees attacked were recorded. Fresh and dry grasses, and litter produced were collected in each section on (0.5 m x 0.5 m) and the termites in the soil were sampling in (0.5 m x 0.5 m x 0.5 m). The fresh and dry grasses, and the litter were collected and weighed.

The termites collected were preserved in 70% ethanol in bottles labeled to show sample station, sample area and collection date.

2.4. Identification of termites

Collected individuals were observed and identified down to the genus level in the laboratory under a binocular magnifying glass, using the identification keys of Sjöstedt (1926), Bouillon and Mathot (1965), Harris (1966a ; 1966b) ; Sands (1965), and Ruelle (1970) , Hellemans *et al.*, (2021). After identification according to Donovan *et al.* (2001), each species was classified into one of the trophic groups (Fungus-growers, Soil-feeders, Wood-feeders and Grass-feeders).

2.5. Evaluation of termite's damage

Some parts of rubber trees destroyed by the termites were also recorded. The attacked trunks were counted per tree and marked so that they were no longer recounted. The damage estimate was obtained from the number of trees attacked.

The damage rates as the percentage of rubber trees attached by termites were calculated using the following formula:

$$Ta = \frac{Npa \times 100}{Ntp} \quad (1)$$

with:

Ta = Damage rates of termites per plot (%)

Npa = Number of plants attacked by termites

Ntp = Total number of sampled plants per plot

2.6. Data analysis

Data of the termite number and termite mounds, termite's damage, grass and litter produced were analyzed using SPSS software, version 22.0. Data were subjected to an analysis of variance (ANOVA main effect) and the means discriminated with the Tukey test (HSD) with a probability of 5 %.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Influence of rubber orchards age on termites diversity

A total of 09 species of termites belonging to 09 genera and 4 sub-families were collected in all the study plot. The Cubitermitinae and Macrotermitinae families were more diversified with 3 species of termite (Table 1). Termites harvested at four trophic groups: wood-feeders, grass/litter feeders, fungus-growers and soil-feeders. The fungus-growers and soil-feeders groups presents with 3 genera were the most diversified groups. In young rubber orchards of class 1 and in rubber orchards of class 3, a total of 5 species of termites were collected. Class 2 recorded the lowest diversity with 4 species of termites collected. Forest recorded the highest diversity with 7 genera of termites collected (Table 1). Wood-feeders and grass or litter feeders were not recorded in rubber orchards of classes 2 and 3. In the forest, grass or litter feeders were not recorded. Two fungus-growers such as *Macrotermes bellicosus*, *Ancistrotermes cavithorax* were recorded in all of the classes of rubber orchards and in the forest. *Odontotermes pauperans* (fungus-growers) were not recorded in rubber orchard of class 1. However, *Amitermes guineensis* (wood-feeders) and *Trinervitermes*

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geminatus (Grass/litter feeders) were only recorded in rubber orchard of class 1 and *Microcerotermes fuscotibialis* (wood-feeders) was only recorded in the forest. *Nitiditermes* sp and *Noditermes* sp (soil-feeders) were recorded in rubber orchard of class 3 and in forest (Table 1).

Table 1. Termite species harvested according to the gradient of rubber plantations

Sub-Families/ Species	FG	Class 1	Class 2	Class 3	Forest
<i>Cubitermitinae</i>					
<i>Procubitermes jöstedti</i>	s	*	*		*
<i>Nitiditermes</i> sp	s			*	*
<i>Noditermes</i> sp	s			*	*
<i>Macrotermatinae</i>					
<i>Macrotermes bellicosus</i>	f	*	*	*	*
<i>Odontotermes pauperans</i>	f		*	*	*
<i>Ancistrotermes cavithorax</i>	f	*	*	*	*
<i>Termitinae</i>					
<i>Amitermes guineensis</i>	w	*			
<i>Microcerotermes fuscotibialis</i>	w				*
<i>Nasutitermitinae</i>					
<i>Trinervitermes geminatus</i>	g	*			
	9	5	4	5	7

FG: feeding groups, f: Fungus-growers; s: soil-feeders, g: Grass/litter feeders; w: wood-feeders

3.2. Influence of rubber orchards age on termites

3.2.1. Influence of rubber orchards age on termite's number and on grass or litter produced

Influence of rubber orchards age on termite's number

The number of termites recorded in all of the rubber orchards classes and in the forest was between 1 to 10 termites per 0.125 m³ of soil. The number of termites decreases progressively with the age of rubber orchards. The number of termite's values were 11.67, 9.44, and 4.61 in rubber orchards of class 1, 2 and 3, respectively. The lowest number of termites was recorded in the forest with 1.61 termites in 0.125 m³ of soil (p=0.001) (Table. 2).

Influence of rubber orchards age on grass or litter produced

In the rubber orchards, the litter produced by termites was higher in rubber orchards of class 1 and was lower in forest. In the rubber orchards of classes 2 and 3, the litter produced by termites were 270.03 g and 286.60 g (p=0.023) (Table 2).

Table 2. Influence of rubber orchards age on termite number and on grass or litter produced

Habitat	Average number of termite \pm SE on 0.125 m ³	Average litter mass (g) \pm SE for 0.25 m ²
Class 1	11.67 c \pm 1.67	330.42 b \pm 8.70
Class 2	9.44 bc \pm 1.31	270.03 ab \pm 16.22
Class 3	4.61 ab \pm 0.89	286.38 ab \pm 38.80
Forest	1.61 a \pm 0.39	244.60 a \pm 4.45
F	15.253	2.792
p	0.001	0.023

SE. Standard error

The means assigned to the same letter within the same column are not significantly different for the 5% Tukey test (HSD).

3.2.2 Influence of rubber orchards age on termites damage and on the number of termite mounds

Influence of rubber orchards age on termites damage

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In the rubber orchards, the termite attacks decreases progressively with the age and were between 8 to 82%. The damage rate was higher on rubber orchards of class 1 (81.67%) and was lower in forest with 8.33 %. The damage rate was 68.33 and 43.33 in rubber orchards of classes 2 and 3, respectively. Statistical analysis showed that attack rates vary according to the age of rubber orchards ($p=0.001$) (Table 3).

Influence of rubber orchards age on the number of termite mounds

In rubber orchards, the highest number of termite mounds was recorded in rubber orchards of class 3 (8.00) and the lowest number was in rubber orchards of class 1 (3.33). The number of termite mounds increased progressively with the age rubber orchards. In rubber orchards of class 2, the number of termite mounds was 7.33. Only the number of termite mounds in rubber orchards of class 1 was lower than those of the forest (5.67). There was a significant difference on number of termite mounds in rubber orchards classes and in the forest ($p= 0.000$) (Table 2).

Table 3. Influence of rubber orchards age on termites damage and on the number of termite mounds

Habitat	Attack rate (%) \pm SE	Average number of termite mounds \pm SE
Class 1	81.67 c \pm 6.01	3.33 a \pm 0.33
Class 2	68.33 c \pm 7.26	7.33 c \pm 0.33
Class 3	43.33 b \pm 3.33	8.00 c \pm 0.57
Forest	8.33 a \pm 3.33	5.67 b \pm 1.61
F	37.425	22.944
p	0.0001	0.000

SE. Standard error

The means assigned to the same letter within the same column are not significantly different for the 5% Tukey test (HSD).

3.2.3 Influence of rubber orchards age on fresh and dry grasses

Termites attack fresh and dry vegetable such as the roots, the stems and the branches on the soil. The highest quantity of fresh grasses were recorded in the rubber orchards of class 1 (37.83 g) and the lowest quantity was in rubber orchards of class 2. The fresh grasses were 27.15 g and 19.53 g in rubber orchards of class 3 and forest, respectively. There was a significant difference between the quantity of fresh grasses in rubber orchards classes and forest ($p= 0.033$) (Table 4).

The dry vegetables occurred in rubber orchards increased with rubber orchard age. The dry vegetables were 84.72 g, 132.97 g and 341.50 g in rubber orchards of class 1, class 2 and class 3, respectively. The dry vegetables occurred in rubber orchards of class 3 were higher than those of the forest (273.71 g) ($p=0.014$) (Table 4).

Table 4. Fresh and dry grasses in the rubber orchards and in the forest on 0.25 m²

Habitat	Fresh grasses (g) \pm SE	Dry grasses (g) \pm SE
Class 1	37.83 b \pm 4.08	84.72 a \pm 11.46
Class 2	12.94 a \pm 5.23	132.97 ab \pm 13.48
Class 3	27.15 ab \pm 6.93	341.50 c \pm 65.13
Forest	19.53 a \pm 1.37	273.71 bc \pm 63.43
F	4.862	6.678
p	0.033	0.014

SE. Standard error

The means assigned to the same letter within the same column are not significantly different for the 5% Tukey test (HSD)

There was a relationship between the number of termites, termite damage and the litter produced, and a relationship between the number of termite mounds and the dry grasses (Figure 2).

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Figure 2. Relationship between termite's activities and the grasses

4. DISCUSSION

4.1. Influence of rubber orchards age on termite's number and their damage, and on litter produced

The results showed that a relationship between the number of termites, termite damage and litter produced. Termites were recorded in all of the rubber orchards classes and in the forest. Similar results were recorded by Tra Bi *et al.*, 2019. They showed that trees were most prone to termite attack. The number of termites decreased progressively with the age of rubber orchards. In fact, farmer used pesticides to protect rubber trees against insect pests. Consequently, the number of termites decreased. Similar results were recorded by Coulibaly *et al.* (2014) in mango orchards.

In the rubber orchards, the termite attacks decreases progressively with the age and were between 8 to 82%. The damage rate was higher on rubber orchards of class 1. During the dry season, termites constitute the most active soil macrofauna (Diop *et al.*, 2013). In search of food, termites attack fresh and dry grasses, and rubber trees, and they break down them into organic matter. So that, termites impacts the quality and the fertility of the soil (Rosin and Leponce, 2004; Jouquet *et al.*, 2011; Freymann *et al.*, 2008). However, the highest damage of termites on rubber trees reduced the yield of this crops (Han and Ndiaye, 1998; Akpesse *et al.*, 2008). The termite pest species harvested in this study belong to the humivorous, fungus-growers, xulophagous and wood-feeders groups. Similar results were recorded by Sane *et al.* (2016) in the region of Senegal. The tree trophic groups, fungus-growers and wood-feeders, are recognized as the main pests of rubber trees (Akpesse *et al.*, 2019; Hidayat *et al.*, 2018) and mango trees (Coulibaly *et al.*, 2014). They attack trees because of their diet mainly based on cellulose and their need for water. The observations of Gbenyedji *et al.* (2016) also showed that most of the termite species responsible for tree damage on the Lomé campus belong to the wood-feeders and fungus-growers groups.

In the rubber orchards, the litter produced by termites was higher in rubber orchards of class 1. In fact, the grass/litter feeders such as *Trinervitermes geminatus* were only recorded in rubber orchards of class 1. Then,

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soil-feeders *Procupitermes jöstedti* was recorded in all classes of rubber orchards and in forest. However the soil-feeders *Nitiditermes* sp and *Noditermes* sp were found in rubber orchards of class 3 and in forest. According to Donovan *et al.* (2001), litter feeders and grass feeders, found foraging leaf litter

4.2. Influence of rubber orchards age on the number of termite's mounds

The results showed that a relationship between the number of termite mounds and the dry grasses of rubber orchards. The number of termite's mounds increased with the dry vegetables occurred in rubber orchards. According to Donovan *et al.* (2001), some termites eat living plants and grass-feeders feed exclusively on grasses.

CONCLUSION

A total of 9 species of termites belonging to 9 genera and 4 sub-families were collected in all the study plot. The Cubitermitinae and Macrotermitinae families were the most diverse with 3 species of termite pests. Termites harvested at four trophic groups: wood-feeders, grass/litter feeders, fungus-growers and soil-feeders. In young rubber orchards ([0, 5] years old) and in rubber orchards of class 3, a total of 5 species of termites were collected. Class 2 recorded the lowest diversity with 4 genera of termites collected. Forest recorded the highest diversity with 7 genera of termites collected. We recommended that the combination of other plants to rubber crops for the insect diversity conservation.

REFERENCES

- i Ahoussi, E.K., N.K. Keumean, M.A. Kouassi, B.Y. Koffi, 2018. *Etude des caractéristiques hydrogéochimiques et microbiologiques des eaux de consommation de la zone périurbaine de la ville de Man : cas du village de Kpangouin (Côte d'Ivoire)*. *International Journal of Biological and Chemical Sciences*, 11(6): 3018-3033. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.4314/ijbcs.v11i6.37>
- ii Akpessa, A.A.M., T.A.P. Kissi, T. Coulibaly, Y.K.S. Diby, K.P. Kouassi, H.K. Koua, 2019. *Termite assemblages and infestation in rubber plantations of M'Brimbo in southern Côte d'Ivoire*. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Biological Sciences*, 6(4): 21-29.
- iii Akpessa, A.A., Kouassi P.K., Tano Y., Lepage M., 2008. *Impact des termites dans les champs paysans de riz et de maïs en savane subsoudanienne (Booro-Borotou, Côte-d'Ivoire)*. *Sciences & Nature*, 5(2): 121-131.
- iv Buchori, D., A. Rizali, G.A. Rahayu, I. Mansur, 2018. *Insect diversity in post-mining areas: Investigating their potential role as bioindicator of reclamation success*. *Biodiversitas*, 19(5) : 1696-1702.
- v Bouillon, A. and G. Mathot, 1965. *Quel est ce termite africain ? Zooleo*, 1 : 1-115
- vi Brou, Y.T., 2005. *Climat, mutations socioéconomiques et paysages en Côte d'Ivoire. Mémoire de synthèse des activités scientifiques présenté en vue de l'obtention de l'Habilitation à Diriger des Recherches, Université des sciences et technologies de Lille, France*, p. 226.
- vii Coulibaly, T., A.A.M. Akpessa, A. Yapi, G.N. Zirihi, K.P. Kouassi, 2014. *Dégâts des termites dans les pépinières de manguiers du nord de la Côte d'Ivoire (Korhogo) et essai de lutte par utilisation d'extraits aqueux de plantes*. *Journal of Animal & Plant Sciences*, 22(3) : 3455-3468.
- viii Diabaté, D. and Y. Tano, 2020. *Efficiences of three insect collection methods in Lamto, Côte d'Ivoire*. *International Journal of Biodiversity and Conservation*, 12(3): 153-158.
- ix Diniz, S., P.I. Prado, T.M. Lewinsohn, 2010. *Species richness in natural and disturbed habitats: Asteraceae and Flower-head insects (Tephritidae: Diptera)*. *Neotropical Entomology*, 39:163-171.
- x Diop, A., A.B. Ndiaye, C.T. Ba, 2013. *Décompositions de la bouse de bovin sèche et macrofaune associée en zone sahélienne semi-aride (Matam, Sénégal)*. *International Journal of Biological and Chemical Sciences*, 7 (1): 147-162.

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- xi Donovan, S.E., P. Eggleton, D.E. Bignell, 2001. Gut content analysis and a new feeding group classification of termites. *Ecological Entomology* 26:356–366. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2311.2001.00342.x>
- xii Eggleton, P., 2000. Global patterns of termite diversity. In: Abe T, Bignel DE, Higashi M (ed) *Termites: Evolution, Sociality, Symbioses, Ecology*. Springer, Netherlands, Dordrecht, pp 25-51.
- xiii Elia, M., R. Laforteza, E. Tarasco, G. Colangelo, G. Sanesi, 2012. The spatial and temporal effects of fire on insect abundance in Mediterranean forest ecosystems. *Forest Ecology and Management*, 263: 262-267.
- xiv Freymann, B.P., R. Buitenwerf, O. Desouza, H. Olf, 2008. The importance of termites (Isoptera) for the recycling of herbivore dung in tropical ecosystem: a review. *European Journal of Entomology*, 105: 165-173. doi :10.14411/eje.2008.025.
- xv Gbenyedji, J.N.B.K., B.D. Kasseney, S. Nyamador, B.B. Sanbena, A.D. Kokutsè, K. Kokou, I.A. Glitho, 2020. Evaluation des attaques de termites (Isoptera Brulle, 1832) sur quatre essences forestières d'importance économique au Togo (Afrique De l'ouest). *European Scientific Journal*, 12(9):332- 352. doi: 10.19044/esj.2016.v12n9p333
- xvi Han, S.H., A.B. Ndiaye, 2006. L'attaque des arbres fruitiers par les termites dans la région de Thiès (Sénégal) (Isoptera). *Bulletin de la société entomologique de France*, 111(1) : 59-64
- xvii Harris, W.V., 1966a. On the genus *Coptotermes* in Africa. *Proceedings of the Royal Entomological Society of London (B)*, 35: 161-171
- xviii Harris, W.V., 1966b. The Genus *Ancistrotermes* (Isoptera). *Bulletin of the British Museum (Natural history) Entomology*, 18(1): 1-20.
- xix Hellemans, S., G. Josens, J.Deligne, Y. Roisin, 2021. Phylogeny and revision of the 'Cubitermes complex' termites (Termitidae: Cubitermitinae) *Systematic Entomology*, 46: 224-238
- xx Hidayat, M.R., W.M. Endris, Y. Dwiyantib, 2018. Effect of a rubber plantation on termite diversity in Melawi, West Kalimantan, Indonesia, *Agriculture and Natural Resources*, 52: 439-444.
- xxi Hunter, P., 2007. The human impact on biological diversity: How species adapt to urban challenges sheds light on evolution and provides clues about conservation. *Embo Reports*, 8:316-318.
- xxii Jouquet, P., S. Traoré, C. Choosai, C. Hartmann, D. Bignell, 2011. Influence of termites on ecosystem functioning. *Ecosystem services provided by termites*. *European Journal of Soil Biology*, 47: 215-222.
- xxiii Keli, J., M.D. Kpolo, G.D. Dea, D. Boa, D. Allet, 1997. L'Hévéaculture en Côte-d'Ivoire : situation actuelle et perspectives. *Plantations Recherche Développement*, 4 (1): 5-10, 1997.
- xxiv Kougbo, M.D., D.F. Malan, M. Dogba, A.S. Konan, 2020. Pratiques culturelles et diversité des ligneux compagnes dans les exploitations cacaoyères et heveicoles à l'est de la Côte d'Ivoire. *African Crop Science Journal*, 28(2) :177-194.
- xxv Muvengwi, J., M. Mbiba, H.G.T. Ndagurwa, G. Nyamadzawo, P. Nhokovedzo, 2017. Termite diversity along a land use intensification gradient in a semi-arid savanna. *Journal of Insect Conservation*, 21:801-812.
- xxvi Roisin, Y., M. Leponce, 2004. Characterizing termite assemblages in fragmented forests: A test case in the Argentinian Chaco. *Austral Ecology*, 29: 637-646.
- xxvii Ruelle, J.E., 1970. A revision of the termites of the genus *Macrotermes* from the Ethiopian region (Isoptera: Termitidae). *Bulletin of the British Museum*, 24 : 363-444.

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- xxviii Saley, M.B., 2003. *Cartographie thématique des aquifères de fissures pour l'évaluation des ressources en eau. Mise en place d'une nouvelle méthode d'extraction des discontinuités images et d'un SIHRS pour la région semi-montagneuse de Man (Nord-Ouest de la Côte d'Ivoire). Thèse de Doctorat d'Université de Cocody-Abidjan, 209 p.*
- xxix Sands, W.A., 1965. *A revision of the termite family Nasutitermitinae (Isoptera, Termitidae) from the Ethiopian Region. Bulletin of the British Museum (Natural History), 4: 1-172.*
- xxx Sane, H., T. Samb, A.B. Ndiaye, T.C. Ba, 2016. *Etude de la diversité des termites (isoptera) dans quelques localités de la région de kolda (Haute Casamance, Sénégal). European Scientific Journal November, 12 (33) : 263-280.*
- doi: 10.19044/esj.2016.v12n33p263
- xxxi Sjöstedt, Y., 1926. *Revision der Termiten Afrikas. 3. Monographie. Kungliga Svenska Vetenskapsakademiens Handlingar, 1-415.*
- xxxii Tra, B.C.S., T. Coulibaly, S.H. Blei, K. Souleymane, K.P. Kouassi, Y. Tano, 2019. *Attacks of termites (Insecta: isoptera) in cocoa farms (Theobroma cacao L.) in Oumé (Côte d'Ivoire). International Journal of Current Research, 11(09): 6899-6905.*